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A study of life style and morbidity profile among geriatric population in Kashmir, India

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Abstract

Objective: To study the life style and morbidity profile of elderly population in Kashmir valley

Study Design: Exploratory in nature with application of quantitative and qualitative research methodology, .multistage sampling, questionnaires/schedules (close ended questions), house to house visit covering all elderly aged above 65 years living in one of the village where a sub center is located, Rural and Urban areas of district Budgam , J and K state.

Patients: Six hundred and ninety two persons aged 65 years and above, 578 from rural and 114 from urban area.

Results: Among 692 elderly registered in the study, 321 were males and 371 were females. A large number of the subjects (89%) were suffering from at least one medical problem. Morbidity among rural subjects was observed to be less when compared to urban subjects. Females had higher rate of morbidity. Common presenting symptoms were pain/ swelling of joints (36.5%), backache (20.2%), indigestion/ heartburn (17.7%), headache (17.4%) and excessive tiredness.

Medical history and physical examination by the physician revealed that most common diseases in order of frequency were hypertension (58%), osteoporosis- (50.55%), cataract (18.51%), gastritis (17.67%) and benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) (13.14%). Most of the elderly female had osteoporosis and the males were suffering from prostate BPH.

Conclusion: Finding from this study support paying attention to the geriatric population, as the prevalence of morbidity among elderly is very high. Thus, there is an urgent need to develop geriatric health care services, and separate geriatric OPDs should be established at all the hospitals. Special hospitals are needed for mental and badly incapacitated old patients

Introduction

Old age is prelude to death. Disease can be cured but not the old age. Population around the world is growing old at high rate with increasing life expectancy. The care of elderly is drawing more and more attention of the government and the public. It is already a major social and health problem in developing countries. Like pediatrics, it deals with an age group that has high morbidity and mortality.

It is ironical that while science has prolonged life, the changes that it has brought about in cultural and social patterns have robbed the elderly of their status and self-esteem and have deprived them of chance to function usefully in the society.

I remember my youth and the feeling that will never come back any more – that feeling that I could last for ever, outlast the sea, the earth, and all men; the deceitful feeling that lures us on to joys, to perils, to love to vain efforts--- to death; the triumphant conviction of strength, the heart of life in the handful of dust, the glow in the heart that every year grows dim, grows cold, grows small and expires- and expires, too soon, too soon ---- before life itself.

Joseph Conrad (Youth-1902)

Patients and Methods

Budgam (also spelt Badgam) means the big village (as in hindi 'Barhagaon') consists of a dry, dusty karewa (plateau) as well as lush meadows, the most famous of which is Yousmarg, it is substantially higher and cooler than the state summer capital. It has an artificial lake (NilNag).Budgam has an area of

1,371sq kms, half of the district consists of forests-750 sq kms.It has substantial Shia (Shiite) population. The Agas are an important spiritual as well as temporal institution among the shias almost everywhere. Its population was estimated at 6, 29,633 lakhs –2001 census, literacy rate 38.47% (the lowest in the state). Urban population 0.71 lakhs, rural population -5.58 lakhs. No. of Households-Rural-76,855; Urban-9,626; with an average household size - 7.3 No's.-2001 census.

The study was conducted in urban and rural areas of District Budgam having about 88.71% population in rural and 11.28% in urban areas. The district has 9 blocks and 121 sub centers. Therefore, the list of all sub centers with approximate number of households was prepared and subsequently a single primary health center (PHC) was chosen for study purposes from each block. Every PHC has approximately ten subcentres working under the supervision of the medical officers posted in PHC, which were selected by stratified random technique in proportion to the population in urban and rural area. The team visited the selected subcentres and conducted the house to house survey i.e. the catchment area of the said sub centre and enquired for the presence of any elderly of the age of 65 years or more. The number of households was decided on the basis of population of the village. A total of 3072 households in rural area and 1072 households in urban area were selected.

A team comprising of director epidemiology, medical officers, health educators, ophthalmological

technician, who were given training in the Regional Institute of Health and Family welfare Dhobi wan Directorate of Health services, Kashmir division, Srinagar, so as to collect uniform information from the subjects. The team from the department visited the selected number of houses and collected information on a pre-designed and pre-tested format. The part-1 of format comprising of general demographic structure of the family was collected by health educator by interviewing with the subjects using interview technique. Part II of the format, comprised of medical history and symptoms. The male and female doctor using the interview technique as per requirement collected data regarding the functional status of elderly. A general and systemic examination was performed. Screening for hearing impairment was assessed by using tuning fork and hearing test and vision was tested by Snellen's chart. The investigations were conducted at the same time. The data was entered in the computer and statistical analysis was done using SPSS software. The study was done over a period of one year in 2006-2007.

Results

In the present study, 4144 families having 30,252 members were visited. There were 692 elderly in the study population and the proportionate geriatric population (65 years and above) constituted 2.28% of the total study population. Twenty seven were not included due to their non-availability in the families. Out of 692 subjects interviewed, 578 were from rural area and 114 from urban area, 321 (42.3%) males, and 371 (57.7%) females. Majority (66.6%) were in the age group

of 65-74 years followed by 26.8% and 6.6% in 75-84 years and 85 years and above age group, respectively.

Common Symptoms	Rural		Urban	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
Pain /swelling in joint	88	116	16	32
Backache	56	43	23	17
Indigestion	22	31	28	41
Headache	53	19	33	16
Vertigo	12	33	3	11
Excessive tiredness	14	8	3	6

Table No: 1:- Common symptoms of the study group. (Rural /Urban).

Total number of illnesses among 692 geriatric populations was 632 as shown in Table 2. Therefore, average number of illnesses per persons was recorded as 3.28. At the time of survey, 88.9% of the study population was suffering from at least one ailment while 69.9%, 47.3% and 16.9% of population was suffering two, three and four or more ailments respectively. Consumption of medicines was taken more adequately and regularly by urban subjects. Health conditions like stroke/paralysis (hemiplegia), cataract and other neurological disorders were responsible of IADL disability.

The data given below in table 3, reveals that most of the elderly population in rural areas were illiterate as compared to the urban subjects. Education status was also found to be an important determinant of disease and disability of elderly people. Population were physically examined and activity of daily living instrumental activity of daily living (ADL/IADL) was assessed in terms of their ability to perform important activities without help-for e.g.:

dressing, toileting , bathing, eating and walking. ADL/IADL disability also increased significantly with relation to age.

Background Characteristics (Morbidity profile of all 632 elderly population)							
Age	Hypertension	osteoporosis	Respiratory problems	Cataract	IHD	Diabetes	BPH
65-75	(56.2%)	32.6%	64.7%	38.7%	19.4%	16.2%	26.3%
75-85	73.2%	69.8%	86.6%	70.6	75.2%	21.6%	83.3%
85 above	83.2%	73.9%	78.5%	62.3	85.6%	52.2%	78.5%

Table 2= Morbidity profile as per the age. 65-75=498; 75-85=93; above 85=41.

Females (65-75) =286 ;(75-85) =51 ;(above 85) =14.

Males (65-75) = 212; (75-85) = 42 ;(above 85) =27.

IHD: - Ischemic heart disease.

BPH: - Benign prostatic hyperplasia.

Characteristics	Rural		Urban	
	Male	female	Male	Female
Education				
High School	21	nil	38	2
Primary	42	05	19	12
Illiterate	196	273	17	26
IADL	28	21	15	17

Table: 3 – showing educational status and IADL disabilities

Discussion

The present study in the district Budgam with over 0.6 million population recorded a high prevalence of morbidity (83.9%) A study carried out in Southern part of India reported a similar result that is a prevalence of 82.9% in the age group of 60 years and above [1] The present study included the geriatric population of 65 years and above as considered by WHO[2]. It is important to make a cut off at 65 years for making global comparisons³. This geriatric age group constituted 6.94% of total population in Budgam.

It was observed that average number of illnesses per person was 1.79 and it was higher in urban community, which may

be due to a higher prevalence of hypertension and myocardial infarction among them. Other studies among elderly in North and South India reported it as 2.627 and 2.42, respectively.⁸

The presenting symptoms of the elderly are significant because patients report to health care providers with these ailments. Thus, health workers and general physicians should be aware of the underlying diseases related to these symptoms. The presenting symptoms of the same disease may vary in elderly in comparison to younger population. Most common symptoms in order of their magnitude were pain/swelling of joints, limitation of movements, headache,

indigestion/ heartburn and excessive tiredness. Prevalence of presenting symptoms did not match with the morbidity profile because many presenting symptoms are not necessarily system specific e.g. heart burn in elderly could be the symptom of GIT or CVS. Many of the diseases were detected on examination and investigations which the patient did not present as specific symptom. Therefore, the purpose of highlighting the problem presenting symptoms is to make the treating physician understand that presenting symptoms and actual disease may not be co-relating. 56.2% of elderly were suffering from hypertension in accordance with the WHO report[2,3] The present study considered a person to be hypertensive with level of blood pressure higher than 140/90 mm of mercury as per the WHO criteria[4]. The presence of hypertension among the elderly in urban areas was about twice that in rural areas. It could be because of sedentary and modern life style and stress in urban areas. Hypertension was more in females as compared to males [1, 5]

A high prevalence of arthritis / joint pain in the current study especially among females was also reported in other studies all over India [1, 2]. Thus reflecting the hard life faced by women who never retire from household work unless totally disabled. 38.7% of elderly were suffering from immature and mature senile cataract. It was more common in males and the prevalence increased with the rising age. Cataract was found to be more common in rural population which may be due to increased exposure to ultraviolet radiation during long hours of work in open fields. The prevalence of blindness

in India is 14.9 per thousand populations. Eighty percent of this blindness is due to cataract alone [6, 7]. National blindness control programme has an important role in reducing the quantum of cataract in the community by organizing eye camps [8]. A number of elderly were suffering from Gastritis because of poor nutrition, increased use of non-steroidal analgesics and indigestion owing to decreased physical activity. It was found to be more common in males; Presence of suspected diabetes mellitus in the elderly further reflects the increasing life-style diseases in the community. And it was again almost three times in females of that of males. In the term of health status, difference between the male and female are clearly explicit in those females who have higher rate of morbidity. In the process of caring and nurturing of other members of the family women in India, invariably tend to neglect or overlook their well being. Prevalence of high morbidity among elderly needs strengthening of geriatric health care services in accordance with the common existing problems in the community. Preventive, curative and rehabilitative programmes for the elderly are required for the control and management of later part of the life [8]

Conclusion

The study among elderly in District Budgam, J&K, and India has highlighted a high prevalence of morbidity and identified common existing medical problems like hypertension, Osteoporosis, Osteoarthritis, Cataract, IHD, BPH and diabetes mellitus. As there is a rapid expansion in number of elderly population, there is an urgent need to develop geriatric health care

services in the developing countries like India and provide training to health care providers to manage the commonly existing health problems in the country. Life style modifications is warranted to prevent onset of chronic disease, to improve quality of life, rectification of poor health status through affordable health service for disease screening and better management of illness and greater health awareness particularly among low- socio economic group could make a difference in quality of elderly kashmiri population.

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